

Hybrid physically based and machine learning model for streamflow prediction

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ABSTRACT

Fully representing the complexity of the rainfall-runoff processes occurring in a catchment for a variety of precipitation events is a challenging task for the physically based hydrological models: the calibration procedure is usually difficult and it might not accurately capture the streamflow response of the catchment for unseen scenarios. In order to achieve a model with enhanced capabilities, this study proposes a methodology to create a hybrid model combining a surrogate model based on the physical model Iber and a machine learning model to compensate for the possible residuals. Since the proposed methodology is designed to be used in early warning system applications, the evaluation is mainly focused on the high streamflow values. The results show that the hybrid model provides higher accuracy than the physically based model and closer approximations to the peak values than a single machine learning model. This results in an increased utility for the intended application. Moreover, it might represent an alternative to the calibration procedure for physically based models.

1. Introduction

Accurate estimation of streamflow is essential in early warning systems (EWS). Physically based models can capture the rainfall-runoff processes but often fail to provide useful estimates of peak flows. In addition, they require a throughout calibration process and relevant computational time. As an alternative, purely data-driven approaches based on machine learning (ML) can provide accurate predictions for high flows in real-time, but require long time series of streamflow data, often unavailable. In addition, the performance of these models usually decreases in extrapolated scenarios (Duan et al., 2020).

To combine the benefits of both approaches and overcome their limitations, we propose a methodology to generate hybrid models for short-term (three hours ahead) flood prediction.

2. Methodology

The predictions of the hybrid model $f(M_{HYB})$ result from the combination of those from a physically based model ($f(M_{PB})$) and from an ML-based model fitted to the residuals of the former ($f(M_{ML,res})$), as follows:

$$Y = f(M_{PB}) + res \quad (1)$$

$$res \approx f(M_{ML,res}) \quad (2)$$

$$Y \approx f(M_{HYB}) = f(M_{PB}) + f(M_{ML,res}) \quad (3)$$

where Y stands for the observed streamflow values and res are the residuals of the M_{PB} .

The hybrid model aims at being useful in EWS applications. Consequently, in order to deliver a quick simulation that is completely focused on the streamflow for the prediction time, this study employs an ML-based surrogate model ($M_{ML,sur}$), instead of the M_{PB} directly, which may be computationally costly (Huang et al., 2021).

Therefore, the overall process includes: a) create a M_{PB} based on Iber (Bladé et al., 2014) and on the physical features of the catchment; b) fit an ML-based surrogate ($M_{ML,sur}$) taking as inputs the accumulated precipitation at several previous time steps; c) compute the residuals of the surrogate; d) fit an ML model to estimate the residuals ($M_{ML,res}$) considering the same inputs as for $M_{ML,sur}$ and adding past streamflow data; e) generate the hybrid model, M_{HYB} , and compute its predictions.

This work employs the Random Forest (RF) (Breiman, 2001) algorithm both for the surrogate and for the residual estimation. To evaluate the performance of the hybrid model, the accuracy of its streamflow predictions are compared to the surrogate ($M_{ML,sur}$) and to a single RF model (M_{ML}) trained with the same variables as the residuals model, as described in López-Chacón et al. (2023).

The study area adopted in this research is the upper Fluvià catchment with outlet point in Olot (Spain). There is one meteorological station and one streamflow gauge within the area (11 years of hourly data). We took 75% of the data for model fitting and the more recent 25% of the data for testing, which contains the highest flows records in the catchment (the Gloria Storm).

3. Results and discussion

The $M_{ML,sur}$ is able to reproduce the Iber simulated streamflow values with a Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) of 0.94 for the Gloria storm hydrograph. For the testing set, the RMSE for streamflow values larger than 75 [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$] ($\text{RMSE}_{Q \geq 75}$) is 30.66 [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$] for $M_{ML,sur}$, 26.62 [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$] for the M_{ML} , and 19,75 [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$] for M_{HYB} . This represents an improvement of 36% and 27% with respect to $M_{ML,sur}$ and to M_{ML} , respectively.

Figure 1 depicts the Gloria storm hydrograph for the observed values and models used for comparison. The M_{ML} underestimates the streamflow peaks, while the $M_{ML,sur}$ shows a considerable overestimation of them and does not capture the first maximum of the hydrograph. The M_{HYB} is able to both capture the first part of the hydrograph and achieve close approximations to the peak values. The M_{ML} is not able to adequately reach high values due to the scarcity of them in the training set. However, this is not a limitation for M_{HYB} , which, supported by the physically based model, is able to predict streamflow peaks with higher accuracy. At the same time, the contribution of $M_{ML,res}$ in the hybrid model is significant, which represents a possible alternative to the calibration process. From the EWS application perspective, M_{HYB} is more suitable due to its higher accuracy overall and especially for high values.

Fig. 1. The Gloria storm hyetograph (half-hourly, green) and hydrograph with the observed, surrogate, single RF, and hybrid models.

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